

Computation of mean errors, correlations, etc

A documentation of the calculations underlying the note IMPROVEMENTS
BY SPACE ASTROMETRY (rev. 78-03-20)

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1. Mean errors of astrometric parameters

The mean errors of the position, proper motion, and parallax of a star of photographic magnitude m at position (λ, β) after 2.5 yr observation are

$$\epsilon_{\lambda \cos \beta} = (2.5/3.0)^{-1/2} F_{\lambda \cos \beta}(\lambda, \beta) \epsilon(m, t) \quad (1)$$

etc (note: exponent $-3/2$ for p.m.). $F(\lambda, \beta)$ are the improvement factors given by ACM for $\zeta = 36^\circ$ and $\epsilon(m, t)$ is the m.e. per scan as function of magnitude and total observing time per year (i.e. the total time per year during which the IFOV is directed onto this star). $\epsilon(m, t)$ is scaled such that for a system of 41 253 stars of magnitude 9 (1 deg^{-2}) we have

$$\boxed{\epsilon(9, 612^{\text{s}}) = 4.5 \text{ marcsec}} \quad (2)$$

$$t = 0.8 (3.16_{10}^7 \text{ s/yr})/41253 = 612^{\text{s}} \text{ (80 \% time efficiency).}$$

The sky averages of $(2.5/3)^x F$ are (according to ACM):

$$\begin{array}{rcl} \lambda \cos \beta & 0.238 & \left. \vphantom{\begin{array}{l} \lambda \cos \beta \\ \beta \end{array}} \right\} 0.203 \\ \beta & 0.167 & \\ \mu_{\lambda \cos \beta} & 0.337 & \left. \vphantom{\begin{array}{l} \mu_{\lambda \cos \beta} \\ \mu_{\beta} \end{array}} \right\} 0.284 \\ \mu_{\beta} & 0.231 & \\ \bar{\omega} & 0.291 & \end{array}$$

The systematic variation with latitude are taken over from my earlier note (78-02-20).

2. Magnitude and time dependence of ϵ

The effects to be included are

- photon noise from the star and background
- jitter
- effects resulting from angle measurement between stars of different intensities.

2.1. Mean error of a single star position in the grid frame

Let t' be the time spent by the IFOV on a star of relative intensity

$I = \text{dex}(-0.4(m - 9))$ during one passage of the star across the FOV.

Considering only photon noise from the star itself the relative accuracy of the observation is given by

$$\sigma^2 = \frac{1}{It'} \quad (3)$$

Introducing a constant background current B (in same unit as I) the variance increases to approximately

$$\sigma^2 = \frac{1 + B/I}{It'} \quad (4)$$

where $I + B$ is the average current.

For the calculations I adopted $B = 0.05$. This is about the geometrical mean of the maximum tolerable value ($B = 0.2$ according to specifications) and the minimum expected (sky averaged) value $B = 0.01$ from faint stars, diffuse galactic light, zodiacal light (away from zodiac) and dark current.

The jitter is assumed to be white and contribute just as much as photon noise for a 9^m star, that is $\sigma_{\text{jitter}}^2 = (1 + B)/t'$. The total variance of the position in the grid system is

$$\sigma^2 = \frac{I + B}{I^2 t'} + \frac{1 + B}{t'} = \frac{f^2(I)}{t'}; \quad f(I) = \frac{1}{I} \sqrt{(1 + B)I^2 + I + B} \quad (5)$$

2.2. Mean error of an angle between two stars

Let I_1 and I_2 be the intensities of two stars connected by an angle measurement. Given the time T available for measuring this connection we should find the optimum division of observing time between the two stars $t'_1 + t'_2 = T$. The accuracy of the angle measurement is

$$\sigma^2 = \frac{f_1^2}{t'_1} + \frac{f_2^2}{T - t'_1}; \quad f_1 = f(I_1), \quad f_2 = f(I_2). \quad (6)$$

This is minimized for

$$t'_1 = \frac{f_1}{f_1 + f_2} T, \quad t'_2 = \frac{f_2}{f_1 + f_2} T, \quad (7)$$

yielding

$$\sigma^2 = \frac{(f_1 + f_2)^2}{T} = \frac{f_1(f_1 + f_2)}{t'_1}. \quad (8)$$

To obtain the mean error per scan as function of m one can argue as follows. It is improbable that a bright star is directly connected to another bright star by an angle measurement. The common situation must be that the bright star is connected to stars of average brightness, say $\bar{m} = 8.6$ for a typical program. And similarly for a faint star. Thus the mean error per scan can be written

$$\epsilon(m, t) = c \sqrt{\frac{f(m)[f(m) + f(\bar{m})]}{t}} \quad (9)$$

It only remains to determine the constant c .

For a program with 41253 stars of $m = 9$ we have $f(m) = f(\bar{m}) = 1.449$, $t = 612^S$ and $\epsilon = 4.5$ marcsec. Hence

$$c = 54.3 \quad (\text{units: s, marcsec}). \quad (10)$$

For Program I and II we adopt $\bar{m} = 8.6$ and $f(\bar{m}) = 1.329$. Together with the improvement factors given above and eq. (1) this will give the stated mean errors.

3. Distribution of observing time

The observing time in Program I is distributed according to (7), i.e. the same time T is spent on all connections (on the average), independent of magnitudes. This is more or less necessary with the sparse system of stars in this program.

In contrast, Program II, with twice as many stars, will make it possible to distribute observing time much more freely. This has been taken advantage of to obtain uniform accuracy except for the faintest stars.

4. Correlation between stars in a small area

The positional errors dv_k along the scan will be slightly correlated because adjacent stars are often connected directly or with few intermediate stars. This effect was studied by computing the autocorrelation function of dv_k obtained from one of my early simulations of step 1 (Note 77-04-15, Table 1, third case). Results are given in Fig. 1.

This correlation is transferred to the astrometric parameters, as shown below. Let x_1, x_2 be parallax errors (position errors, p.m. errors) of two stars close to each other. The least-squares solution takes the form

$$x_i = \sum_j a_{ij} dv_{k(i,j)} \quad (11)$$

where $k(i,j)$ denotes the observation of star i during the group of scans indexed j . a_{ij} are known factors. For two stars in a small field $a_{1j} \approx a_{2j}$. Thus

$$E(x_1^2) \approx E(x_2^2) = \sum_j \sum_{j'} a_{2j} a_{2j'} E(dv_{k(2,j)} dv_{k(2,j')}),$$

$$E(x_1 x_2) = \sum_j \sum_{j'} a_{1j} a_{2j'} E(dv_{k(1,j)} dv_{k(2,j')}). \quad (12)$$

But we may assume that observations in different groups are uncorrelated,

$$E(dv_{k(1,j)} dv_{k(2,j')}) = \delta_{jj'} \sigma_{dv}^2 \rho_{12} \quad (13)$$

where $\sigma_{dv}^2 = E(dv_k^2)$ and ρ_{12} = correlation between $dv_{k(1,j)}$ and $dv_{k(2,j)}$. The correlation between x_1 and x_2 is then

$$\rho_{x_1 x_2} = E(x_1 x_2) [E(x_1^2) E(x_2^2)]^{-1/2} \approx \rho_{12}, \quad \text{Q.E.D.} \quad (14)$$

Fig. 1. Normalized autocorrelation of positional errors along a reference circle. $\gamma = 64^\circ$, FOV: $0.9 \times 1.2 \text{ deg}^2$, density 1 deg^{-2} , 8 scans.